

Milestone: M6.2 Mirror groups survey

Lead Participant:

ISCIII

Author:

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Due:

31 Oct 2020

Date Of Completion:

08 Oct 2020

Means of Verification

<https://www.surveymonkey.com/r/C292V7Q>

Milestone Delayed (if yes, please explain)

No.

Project participants & others

The survey has been designed by ISCIII and other WP6 members.

The survey must be answered by the members of WG1 or the national representatives of the member states.

Next action steps

Kind reminder on 14 Oct 2020.

The answers must be analysed before the Commission Special Group on 26th November 2020.

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